

Entanglement Fidelity and Circuit Accuracy in Distributed Quantum Computing

by

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Abstract

Distributed quantum computation (DQC) can involve using multiple physical quantum computers interconnected with quantum channels to execute large quantum circuits. Doing this requires high fidelity quantum channels and partitioning a circuit effectively across different quantum computers. There has been large quantities of research into these problems. But there have been no published actual simulations of imperfect DQC: executing a circuit distributed across multiple quantum computers connected with imperfect channels. In this thesis I simulate distributed random circuit sampling and calculate the linear cross entropy benchmark fidelity (XEB) in scenarios where the connecting quantum channels have fidelities ranging from perfect to low. We see from simulations that a fidelity of 0.99 is necessary to get a high XEB and discuss why this is the case.

1 Introduction

Distributed quantum computation is the act of partitioning a n qubit circuit such that it can be executed on quantum computers of less than n qubits. There are many ways this can be done. From executing the entire circuit using non-local gates, gates on qubits that are located on different quantum computers. To using “gate cutting” and “wire cutting” methods to execute parts of a circuit separately and using classical post-processing to obtain a result equivalent to executing the entire circuit. In this thesis we will focus on distributed entire circuit computation using non-local gates.

The main focus of this thesis is on simulating entire distributed quantum circuits to understand how the entanglement fidelity of ebits (a resource used to carry out non-local gates) affects the linear cross entropy benchmark fidelity in random circuit sampling. This is an entirely novel contribution to the literature. The literature so far in entire circuit distributed quantum computation has focused on one of two things. The first is the optimisation problem: how do partition our circuit across multiple quantum computers such that qubits are placed on different quantum computers in a way that minimises the number of non-local gates? This problem is important because non-local gates are thought to be much more expensive and noisy than local operations. This problem has been studied in work such as [1, 2]. The second problem is the entanglement fidelity problem. Non-local gates require high fidelity entangled qubits between quantum computers to be carried out effectively. The question is: how do we create high fidelity entangled qubits between quantum computers and what conditions are sufficient for this? This has been studied in work such as [3–5].

There are four main sections to this report. In the Background Theory section I explain what non-local gates are and what circuit distribution/partitioning entails. In the Literature Review section I explain the work of related papers and how they have not done what I have done in this work. In the Methodology section I explain how distributed circuits were created and simulated. In the Results section I discuss the results of the simulations and distributions.

2 Background Theory

2.1 Non-local gate operations.

Non-local gate operations are two qubit gates that are carried out between qubits located on two different nodes. These operations require only local operations on each node and classical communication between them (LOCC), and an “ebit” (cite). An ebit is a pair of qubits, one on each node, that are in the bell state $|\phi^+\rangle$.

The process has three steps:

1. Share a qubit A1 on one node (A) with another node (B). This is often called the 'cat-entangler' stage, or in some software libraries the 'starting process' stage. The qubit is shared to a “link” or “communication” register on B.
2. Execute desired local operations between the shared qubit in the link register and other qubits on the same node. These are equivalent to if A1 was physically located on B.
3. Remove the qubit from the link register. This means that we can now able to modify its state, for example carrying out gate operations where it is a target. We are not typically able to do that whilst it is being shared with other nodes. This process is often called the 'cat-disentangler' stage or the 'ending process'.

Figure 1: A non-local CNOT gate with qubit A1 located on node A as the control and qubit B2 located on node B the target. Our ebit is qubit A2 and B1 and its presence is shown by the wavy line between the qubits. Qubit B1 acts as a link register for B. The blue box represents node A and the red box represents node B. The green box is the cat-entangler process. The purple box is the cat-disentangler process. Labels and boxes added to the original circuit diagram from [6].

Using figure 1, the specific operations are as follows. For the cat-entangler stage, apply a CNOT between A1 and A2. Measure A2. If the measurement reads 1, apply an X gate to B1. Otherwise do nothing. Apply our desired operations between B1 and B2 (where B1 is the same state as A1). Carry out the cat-disentangler stage. This involves applying a Hadamard gate to A1 followed by measuring B1. If B1 reads 1, apply a Z gate to A1. Otherwise do nothing.

2.2 The circuit distribution problem

We know now how to carry out non-local gate operations between different nodes. But, there is still the question of *how* to distribute a circuit across multiple nodes: what qubits do we place on each node?. We call this operation Circuit Distribution [1]. We can either optimise our placement of qubits such to reduce the circuit depth (cite martinez). Or we can optimise our placement of qubits to minimise the number of ebits used. We focus on the latter target. We call the problem the DQC problem. Colloquially we can think of the problem as the following: if we have three qubits q1 q2 and q3 and we want to split them across two nodes, then which qubits do we place where? Optimising to minimise the number of ebits, if q1 and q3 have much more 2 qubit gates between them than other combinations, then we should place q1 and q3 on the same node so that only local operations and no ebits are needed for their operations.

2.3 What entanglement fidelity is

Telegate (and teledata) methods of distributed quantum computing rely on high fidelity ebit resources. The lower the fidelity the more our ebit resource is 'mixed' which in the quantum sense means that it is a classically probabilistic mixture of different states, then our bit state is something other than a pure bell state and therefore - when we apply the cat-entangler method - will not perfectly share a qubit.

Entanglement fidelity is the overlap between an initially pure quantum state before it was sent through a channel and its state after it was sent through a channel. [7]. Formally for a quantum system consisting of qubits R and Q where Q is sent through a channel \mathcal{E} :

$$F_e(|\psi^{RQ}\rangle\langle\psi^{RQ}|, \mathcal{E}) = \langle\psi^{RQ}|(\mathcal{I}_R \otimes \mathcal{E})(|\psi^{RQ}\rangle\langle\psi^{RQ}|)|\psi^{RQ}\rangle$$

These definitions are the same as the standard definition of fidelity between a pure state and a mixed state given in [8]:

$$F_e(|\psi^{RQ}\rangle\langle\psi^{RQ}|, \rho_2) = \langle\psi^{RQ}|\rho_2|\psi^{RQ}\rangle$$

where ρ_2 is the state of the system after R has been through the channel. They just have the benefit of making the quantum channel explicit. Essentially we are measuring the probability that ρ_2 is our original pure state $|\psi^{RQ}\rangle$.

These definition assumes that only one of the two qubits has been put through a quantum channel. In this thesis we will cover situations where both qubits have gone through a

quantum channel. This corresponds to a physical situation that I believe will be typical in distributed quantum computing. One where a central source transmits an entangled photon pair to two quantum computers. Clearly both photons/qubits encounter noise and therefore this must be accounted for. In this case, our definition where R and Q are sent through physically identical but different channels:

$$F_e(|\psi^{RQ}\rangle\langle\psi^{RQ}|, \mathcal{E}) = \langle\psi^{RQ}|(\mathcal{E}_R \otimes \mathcal{E}_Q)(|\psi^{RQ}\rangle\langle\psi^{RQ}|)|\psi^{RQ}\rangle$$

The above definitions are special cases of a more complex definition of fidelity given in [8] where both our input and output states are mixed. But we can use them since we assume that our original state is pure.

2.3.1 Quantum Channels

Quantum channels are used to express different types of error. The quantum channel we are most concerned with is the depolarising channel. This channel represents the random effect of X, Y and Z operations on qubits and is often used to model situations such as photons travelling through space. Applied to n qubits with a density matrix ρ , we write the channel as:

$$\mathcal{E}(\rho) = (1 - p)\rho + \frac{pI_n}{2^n}$$

where I_n is the entirely mixed state [9]. An entirely mixed state is a uniform mixture of states in the chosen orthonormal basis. In the computational basis for a single qubit $I_1 = |0\rangle\langle 0| + |1\rangle\langle 1|$. The depolarising channel can be thought of as a channel that with probability $(1 - p)$ our state is unchanged but with probability p it has been completely depolarised to the state $I_n/2$.

Equivalently, we can write the channel as:

$$\mathcal{E}(\rho) = (1 - p)\rho + \frac{p}{3}(X\rho X + Y\rho Y + Z\rho Z)$$

which makes clear that “ ρ is left alone with probability $1 - p$, and the operators X, Y and Z applied each with probability $p/3$.”[10] See appendix for derivation. This form makes clear where the idea of the channel comes from, that it is meant to represent the standard noise operations that can happen to it (flesh out!).

In the physical situation we aim to simulate two entangled photons going through different fibre optics with noise parameter p .

When applying an error channel on a single qubit R that's part of a larger system ρ , we use the definition:

$$(\mathcal{I}_R \otimes \mathcal{E}_Q)(\rho) = (1 - p)\rho + pTr_Q(\rho) \otimes \frac{I_1}{2}$$

from [9]. So, to simulate a separate error channel being applied to both R and Q we need to apply:

$$(\mathcal{E}_R \otimes \mathcal{I}_Q)(\mathcal{I}_R \otimes \mathcal{E}_Q) = (\mathcal{E}_R \otimes \mathcal{E}_Q)$$

In this thesis, our shared ebit is $|\Phi^+\rangle = 1/\sqrt{2}(|00\rangle_{RQ} + |11\rangle_{RQ})$. This has density matrix $|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| = 1/2(|00\rangle\langle 00| + |00\rangle\langle 11| + |11\rangle\langle 00| + |11\rangle\langle 11|)$ which gives $Tr_R(\rho) = Tr_Q(\rho) = I_2/2$.

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{E}_R \otimes \mathcal{E}_Q)|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| &= (\mathcal{E}_R \otimes \mathcal{I}_Q)((1-p)\rho + p\frac{I_2}{4}) \\ (\mathcal{E}_R \otimes \mathcal{E}_Q)|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| &= (1-p)[(1-p)\rho + p\frac{I_2}{4}] + pTr_R[(1-p)\rho + p\frac{I_2}{4}] \otimes \frac{I_1}{2} \\ (\mathcal{E}_R \otimes \mathcal{E}_Q)|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| &= p(2-p)\frac{I_2}{4} + (1-p)^2|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| \end{aligned}$$

Writing $\lambda = p(2-p)$ we get:

$$(\mathcal{E}_R \otimes \mathcal{E}_Q)|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| = \lambda\frac{I_2}{4} + (1-\lambda)|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+|$$

And we see that we recover the 2 qubit function (y). This is interesting because x. But doing this calculation has allowed us to calculate λ as a function of p .

To calculate the fidelity as a function of p , we expand I_2 :

$$(\mathcal{E}_R \otimes \mathcal{E}_Q)|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| = \lambda(|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| + |\Phi^-\rangle\langle\Phi^-| + |\Psi^+\rangle\langle\Psi^+| + |\Psi^-\rangle\langle\Psi^-|) + (1-\lambda)|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+|$$

$$(\mathcal{E}_R \otimes \mathcal{E}_Q)|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| = (1 - \frac{3\lambda}{4})|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| + \frac{\lambda}{4}(|\Phi^-\rangle\langle\Phi^-| + |\Psi^+\rangle\langle\Psi^+| + |\Psi^-\rangle\langle\Psi^-|)$$

This is called a Werner state and, as we will see, has the useful property that the fidelity F is explicitly present.

Applying the definition of fidelity from (x) we get:

$$F = \langle\Phi^+|(\mathcal{E}_R \otimes \mathcal{E}_Q)|\Phi^+\rangle = \langle\Phi^+|(1 - \frac{3\lambda}{4})|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| + \frac{\lambda}{4}(|\Phi^-\rangle\langle\Phi^-| + |\Psi^+\rangle\langle\Psi^+| + |\Psi^-\rangle\langle\Psi^-|)|\Phi^+\rangle$$

$$\begin{aligned} F &= 1 - \frac{3\lambda}{4} \\ F &= \frac{4 - 6p - 3p^2}{4} \end{aligned}$$

Giving us:

$$(\mathcal{E}_R \otimes \mathcal{E}_Q)|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| = F|\Phi^+\rangle\langle\Phi^+| + \frac{(1-F)}{3}(|\Phi^-\rangle\langle\Phi^-| + |\Psi^+\rangle\langle\Psi^+| + |\Psi^-\rangle\langle\Psi^-|)$$

2.3.2 Mathematical Effects of Lower Fidelity

When there is noise, there is a $1 - F$ probability that our shared ebit is one of $|\Phi^-\rangle$, $|\Psi^+\rangle$, $|\Psi^-\rangle$ rather than $|\Phi^+\rangle$. $|\Phi^-\rangle$ does not affect a non-local CNOT but $|\Psi^+\rangle$ and $|\Psi^-\rangle$ have the effect of causing a bit flip on the target qubit when a non-local CNOT is carried out. This means that the CNOT is carried out, but it is followed by an unwanted X gate on the target qubit. Therefore, for a fidelity F there is a $\frac{1+2F}{3}$ probability that our non-local CNOT will be carried out without errors and a $\frac{2(1-F)}{3}$ probability that it will be carried out with a bit flip error on the target qubit. The matrix representing the operation when our ebit is in the state $|\Psi^+\rangle$ or $|\Psi^-\rangle$ is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Clearly, if a qubit is the target of two adjacent non-local CNOTs there is a $(\frac{2(1-F)}{3})^2$ probability that it will be unaffected by the error. Otherwise, an error will be introduced to the circuit. In circuits without this structure, the probability of getting the right answer is $(\frac{1+2F}{3})^k$ where k is the number of non-local CNOT gates.

2.4 Adder Circuit

The plain quantum adder is a simple and non-optimised circuit that adds two n -bit binary numbers represented by qubits in the state $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$ using $3n + 1$ qubits using only CNOT and Toffoli gates [11]. In the literature, adder circuits are used as sub-routines for more advanced circuits. On their own, they are clearly useless. But the plain quantum adders simplicity, regular structure and right/wrong answer makes it easy to understand and analyse. For example, measuring the relevant bits of an adder that has added 0,1 1,0 should yield 11 100% of the time.

Figure 2: “Plain adder network. In the first step, all the carries are calculated until the last carry gives the most significant digit of the result. Then all these operations apart from the last one are undone in reverse order, and the sum of the digits is performed correspondingly. Note the position of a thick black bar on the right- or left-hand side of basic carry and sum networks. A network with a bar on the left side represents the reversed sequence of elementary gates embedded in the same network with the bar on the right side.” [11]

Figure 3: What each “sum” or “carry” box represents. [11]

2.5 Random Circuit Sampling

Random circuit sampling is a technique to test the capability of quantum computers. The idea is to carry out a circuit that effectively represents a random unitary matrix and then ‘sample’ that circuit by measuring it repeatedly. The probability of the different bit string outcomes e.g 00011001 should follow what is called the Porter-Thomas distribution. If our bit-string outcomes were the product of random uniform noise, we would expect them to follow the uniform distribution: every bit string is equally probable. But the special mathematical structure of random quantum circuits gives rise to a different distribution.

Figure 4: The Porter-Thomas distribution. In our case, Np is the scaled probability of measuring a fixed bit string and e^{-Np} is the probability that our bit string has that probability. $N = 2^n$ is the number of different bit-strings possible in a n -qubit circuit. Effectively, the Porter-Thomas distribution shows that we should expect many bit-strings that have a low probability of being measured and a few that have a high probability of being measured.

The reason why this technique is interesting is two fold. The first is that it is computationally difficult for classical computers. Random unitary matrices possess no symmetries and are spread out over Hilbert space [12]. This means that they cannot be 'sliced up' to make calculation easier. Therefore, effectively, sampling the state produced by a random circuit requires calculating 2^n by 2^n matrix that represents the circuit and computing the state. The resources needed to do this increase exponentially [12]. There are no shortcuts because the chaotic nature of the evolution described by the matrix means that sampling the state requires calculating it explicitly [12]. There are also theoretical computational complexity arguments for why this problem is classically hard [13].

The second reason why it is interesting is because it allows us to benchmark the capability of a quantum computer. If the quantum computer is able to perfectly produce a state acted upon by a random unitary matrix, then it has perfectly maintained the state throughout the circuit and every gate acted on it has been perfect. If we sample a supposedly random state and it produces uniformly bit-strings or bit-strings that are biased in the wrong way, then clearly our quantum computer is not entirely capable of carrying out its function.

A quantity called the linear cross entropy difference (XEB) has been developed to characterise the difference between the distribution of the probability of the sampled bit strings of a perfect quantum computer compared to a noisy experiment implementation or classical

simulation Arute2019. It has the following form:

$$\mathcal{F}_{XEB} = \frac{2^n}{k} \sum_x \langle x | \psi \rangle - 1$$

[14]. If F_{XEB} is 0, we have sampled from the uniform distribution and therefore our quantum computer or classical algorithm is too noisy or inaccurate. If F_{XEB} is 1, we are sampling from a perfect quantum computer (within statistical error).

It is useful to understand how F_{XEB} has been derived from the Porter-Thomas distribution. I will rephrase the explanation in [14]. We know that the fraction of bit-strings with a probability in the interval $[p, p + dp]$ follows the Porter-Thomas distribution Pr and therefore is:

$$Pr(p)dp = Ne^{-D=Np}$$

with the total number of bit strings being:

$$N(p)dp = (N)(Ne^{-Np}) = N^2e^{-Np}$$

Therefore the probability that a bit string in our interval $[p, p + dp]$ is measured when a random circuit is ran on a quantum computer is:

$$pN(p)dp = pN^2e^{-Np} = f(p)dp$$

where $f(p)$ now represents the probability density function of sampling a bit string with probability p . If you were to produce a normalised graph of bit-strings where the probability p determined by the state vector is the x value and the number of times it was measured is the y value then the graph should match $f(p)$.

We then take the expectation value of $f(p)$ which tells us the “average probability of a sampled bit string:

$$E(f(p)) = \int_0^1 pf(p) dp = \int_0^1 pN^2e^{-Np} dp$$

$$E(f(p)) = \frac{2}{N}(1 - e^{-N}(\frac{N^2}{2} + N + 1)) \approx \frac{2}{N}$$

If we rewrite F_{XEB} as:

$$\mathcal{F}_{XEB} = N \sum_i \frac{m_i}{k} \langle x_i | \psi \rangle - 1$$

where m_i is the number of times we’ve measured x_i . Then in the limit

$$\mathcal{F}_{XEB} = NE_{experiment}(f(p)) - 1$$

We can now see that if we substitute this into our equation blah, we get 1. Clearly, if the probability that we measure certain bit strings is truly governed by the Porter-Thomas distribution, then F_{XEB} should equal 1.

2.5.1 How I generated random circuits

To generate random circuits that approximate random unitary matrices I followed the approach in [15]. The method consists of applying the following "cycle" k times on n qubits. Firstly, apply a different random unitary matrix to every qubit. Then apply the following operator: $U = \exp[i(\frac{\pi}{4}) \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \sigma_z^j \otimes \sigma_z^{j+1}]$ which means applying a CZZ gate between nearest neighbor qubits on a line topology.

3 Brief Literature Review

3.1 The pytketdq library compared to previous work

Martinez et al's pytketdq library and the paper it was published with [1] is the most advanced method of partitioning. The library and paper are notable in that they extend automated partitioning to heterogeneous networks: ones where node sizes can greatly vary and each node may not be connected to every other node. This is less useful to us but may be useful in future research. What is important is the performance of the library for homogeneous all to all connected networks of nodes (those which we will be simulating in this work). For this, the library performs better than previous works and has the advantage that it is publicly available.

Figure 5: The ebit cost compared to the fraction of controlled-Z gates in different sized circuits for random circuits (different from those discussed in this work) distributed across different numbers of nodes. G* techniques are techniques from other researches, the rest are those developed by Martinez et al. Chart from [1]

Figure 6: The ebit cost compared to the fraction of controlled-Z gates in different sized circuits for random circuits (different from those discussed in this work) distributed across different numbers of nodes. G* techniques are techniques from other researches, the rest are those developed by Martinez et al. Chart from [1]

We use the EmbedSteinerDetach technique when distributing our circuits in this work. We see it compares favourably to other techniques.

3.2 Related work on simulating components of distributed quantum computation.

There are three key papers from the literature that involve work related to simulating parts of a distributed entire circuit computation [3–5]. I will briefly describe the work of one paper and how they have not carried out simulations of computations of entire circuits as I have done in this work.

In [3] they describe a possible distributed architecture consisting of 4 qubit nodes connected to nearest neighbours via quantum channels. They show that with quantum channels of fidelity approx 0.7 and local operations with error probability 0.1%, it is possible to use entanglement pumping to achieve high fidelity ebits.

Figure 7: Contour plots of ebit infidelity ($1 - F - ebit$) with quantum channel fidelity F against local operation error probability p_g . They define fault tolerant non-local computation as that which produces an ebit with fidelity of 0.99 which they chose because it is sufficient for error correction schemes. From [3].

Their calculations are all numerical and do not come from simulation of the computation of the distributed circuit. But the result is extremely useful as it shows that with imperfect channels and local operations we can achieve high fidelity.

4 Methodology

4.1 Distributing a circuit and executing it

I will now describe how I distribute circuits and then convert them into a monolithic qiskit circuit that I can simulate.

After inputting a circuit and network to `pytket_dqc`, it returns the following: (1) a list of qubits with the servers they belong to and their type (computational or communication) (2) the series of gate operations to be carried out, including `starting_process` and `ending_process`, and (3) a mapping between the new qubits and the monolithic qubits. `starting_process` corresponds to creating an ebit between the relevant servers and carrying out the cat entangler operations. `ending_process` corresponds to the cat-disentangler operation.

From this, I construct a monolithic Qiskit circuit where qubits q_0 to q_k represent the qubits of `server_0`, qubits q_{k+1} to q_l represent the qubits of `server_1` and henceforth. Qubits have the order of computational, communication and temporary. A temporary qubit is a qubit that becomes entangled with a communication qubit on a relevant node when we need to share a computational qubit with it. Each “node” within my monolithic qiskit circuit has either 0 or 1 temporary qubits depending on whether it is required to share a computational qubit in the output given by `pytket_dqc`. Otherwise the number of computational and communication qubits matches the output of `pytket_dqc`. Therefore, my monolithic qiskit circuit has at maximum the number of qubits outputted by `pytket_dqc` plus the number of nodes.

Each `starting_process` between `pytket_dqc` qubit `server_j[k]` and `server_l.link_register[m]` is replaced with the following operations: (1) Apply a H gate on `server_j[k]`'s temporary qubit followed by a CNOT with the temporary qubit control and `server_l.link_register[m]` target. This creates a perfect Bell State Pair $|\psi\rangle$ ebit between them as required. (2) Apply noise to $|\psi\rangle$, if any. (3) Apply the standard set of cat-entangler operations. `server_j[k]` is now shared with `server_l` via `server_l.link_register[m]`. Measured qubits are reset to $|0\rangle$ For `ending_process`, we follow the standard cat-disentangler procedure between `server_j[k]` and `server_l.link_register[m]`.

For measurement of computational qubits at the end, we must ensure that only the qubits from the original server we want are measured. I do this by using the mapping between the original circuit and the distributed circuit provided by `pytket_dqc` combined with the mapping I produce between the monolithic circuit and the `pytket_dqc` output.

4.2 Network architecture

Circuits are distributed on a homogeneous architecture of approximately equal sized nodes where all qubits within a node can communicate with each other. For each set number of servers, say 3, an architecture is passed to `pytket_dqc` increasing in size until a valid distribution is given. For example, a circuit to be distributed across 3 nodes would be given an architecture where every server has 1 qubits and then 2 qubits until a valid distribution is given.

4.3 Sanity checks

Programs such as Qiskit compile circuits they are given before they are ran. This includes replacing sets of appropriate gates with a single equivalent gate. This could clearly change my circuit such that my desired structure - which perfectly replicates the computation of a distributed circuit - is changed and therefore does not achieve this. I used the compiler command `optimization_level=0` and `barriers` to prevent this from happening.

4.4 Random Circuit Sampling

For a circuit size of 7 and 10 qubits, 10 different random circuits were generated giving 20 circuits in total. Each circuit was distributed on 2 to 4 servers for the 7 qubit circuit and 2 to 6 for the 10 qubit circuit. A monolithic circuit was produced using the method described above. In total 80 monolithic qiskit circuits were produced. Each circuit was then executed with an entanglement fidelity of 1, 0.9999, 0.999, 0.99 and 0.9. Therefore, each circuit was ran 5 times, each time with a different fidelity. For each run, the circuit was sampled 2000 times and the quantity $\langle x_i | \psi \rangle$ was calculated where $|\psi\rangle$ is the state vector of the original non-distributed circuit. The XEB was then calculated and averaged over the 10 random circuits. Therefore for each combination of original circuit size, fidelity and number of servers distributed across, the XEB was calculated for 10 different random circuits and averaged.

5 Results

5.0.1 Distribution on to homogenous servers

Figure 8: The number and types of gates used by a 7-qubit random circuit that uses has 40 cycles of 7 one qubit gates and 6 two qubit gates. Because of the regular structure of the circuit we see that the number of ebits and non-local gates increases by the same amount as we increasingly distribute the circuit.

Figure 9: The number and types of gates used by a 10-qubit random circuit that uses has 40 cycles of 10 one qubit gates and 9 two qubit gates. Because of the regular structure of the circuit we see that the number of ebits and non-local gates increases by the same amount as we increasingly distribute the circuit. This regular structure also means that we require the same number of ebits for the same number of servers as the 7-qubit random circuit.

The number of ebits and non-local gates increases monotonically for both servers. Interestingly, each non-local gate uses exactly one ebit. This is because of the structure of the circuit. Since two qubit gates in the original circuit act on a line topology where every cycle every qubit other than the first and last is used as both a target and control qubit, we cannot reuse ebits to carry out multiple non-local gates. This is because after a cycle k where a qubit that has been used as a control qubit for a non-local gate, that qubit will be the target of another qubit and therefore must be “disentangled”. When that qubit is used as a control qubit again, it must be re-entangled. We clearly see how the number of non-local gates follows a trend of being equal to the number of cycles times the number of servers the circuit is distributed across.

Additionally, the regular structure on a line topology and the one ebit to one non-local gate relationship means that distributing a 100 qubit circuit on to any number of servers requires the same number of ebits and non-local gates as distributing a 10 qubit circuit on

to the same number of servers. This is why we see that the 7 and 10 qubit circuit have the same ebit and non-local gate usage for the same number of servers.

5.0.2 Qubit usage

Figure 10: The number and types of qubits used by a 7-qubit adder circuit distributed on two to four servers.

Figure 11: The number and types of qubits used by a 7-qubit adder circuit distributed on two to four servers.

The number of communication and entanglement space qubits is equal to the number of servers being distributed across for the servers and circuit sizes we tested. If this trend continues then as the number of servers approaches half the number of qubits used in the original circuit, then the number of non-computational qubits will equal the number of computational qubits.

What we clearly see in the case of qubit and gate usage is that the extremely connected and regular structure of our random circuit prevents `pytket_dqc` from optimising the number of ebits. The number of ebits and non-computational qubits used generally matches a naive distribution.

5.0.3 XEB Results

Figure 12: The linear cross entropy benchmark fidelity averaged across 10 random 7 qubit circuits distributed on 2 to 4 servers with varying entanglement fidelity. To use a log scale, the x axis shows 1 minus the fidelity. A fidelity of 0.999 therefore corresponds to 10^{-3} on the x axis. Fidelity of 1 is shown where the line graph intercepts the y axis. We see that perfect fidelity to extremely high fidelity has a XEB of 1, as expected. XEB monotonically decreases as fidelity decreases.

Figure 13: The linear cross entropy benchmark fidelity averaged across 10 random 10 qubit circuits distributed on 2 to 6 servers with varying entanglement fidelity. To use a log scale, the x axis shows 1 minus the fidelity. A fidelity of 0.999 therefore corresponds to 10^{-3} on the x axis. Fidelity of 1 is shown where the line graph intercepts the y axis. We see that perfect fidelity to extremely high fidelity has a XEB of roughly 1, as expected. XEB monotonically decreases as fidelity decreases.

For the sample of we have tested, namely 7 and 10 qubit random circuits, the size of the original circuit does not seem to affect the XEB. Distributed on the same number of servers, with the same entanglement fidelity, it seems that the XEB is the same for the 7 and 10 qubit circuits. There is a very clear trend that increasing the number of servers or decreasing the entanglement fidelity decreases the XEB. This is entirely expected since the greater the number of non-local gates, the larger the number of errors introduced into the circuit. As discussed in the background theory, each non-local gate has a $\frac{2(1-F)}{3}$ probability of introducing a bit flip error. For all numbers of servers, below an entanglement fidelity of 0.99, we get a XEB around zero: our circuits are simply producing uniform noise. Clearly if we wish to achieve useful results we need to have an entanglement fidelity of 0.99.

This is far from impossible. Entanglement pumping allows us to use multiple noisy ebits to construct a single less noisy ebit. The only upper bound on this method is the noise of our local operations. If for example we had a physical set up that could not produce ebits with fidelity above 0.99, we could still produce ebits above this fidelity using entanglement pumping if the error rate of our local one and two qubit operations was sufficient.

Figure 14: The linear cross entropy benchmark fidelity estimated from the entanglement fidelity and the number of non-local gates for 7 qubit random circuits.

Figure 15: The linear cross entropy benchmark fidelity estimated from the entanglement fidelity and the number of non-local gates for 10 qubit random circuits. This is identical to the 7 qubit graph (other than increasing the number of servers) because for each number of servers distributed across, the number of non-local gates is the same for the 7 and 10 qubit case.

We can clearly see that the XEB estimated from $\frac{2(1-F)}{3}$ lines up very well with our experimental results. This is because XEB is approximately also a measure of circuit fidelity.

Figure 16: The normalised number of occurrences of bit-strings with probabilities of measurement p derived from the state vector for a 10 qubit random circuit distributed across 5 servers with perfect ebit fidelity.

Figure 17: The normalised number of occurrences of bit-strings with probabilities of measurement p derived from the state vector for a 10 qubit random circuit distributed across 5 servers with the lowest possible ebit fidelity.

We also see that the XEB quantity as described in the background theory clearly captures the behaviour we want: that it is 1 when our measurements line up with the expected distribution and 0 when bit-strings are distributed uniformly randomly. The distribution in the case where our fidelity is maximally low is interesting: it is the same as the distribution of the measurement probabilities of bit strings as determined by the Porter-Thomas distribution. Yet we would expect the distribution of the number of times we measured certain bit-strings to be different, as we derived in the background theory. The reason why in the worst case it matches the Porter-Thomas distribution is because it shows that the bit strings are being measured without regard for their intrinsic probabilities of being measured. If you were to uniformly sample from the Porter-Thomas distribution, you would expect to get the Porter-Thomas distribution. Essentially what is happening is that our bit-strings are simply being uniformly sampled: our circuit has degraded into random noise and we have lost any structure.

6 Conclusion

We have met the main objective of the project. We have correctly carried out simulations of entire circuit distributed quantum computation. What we have seen is that distributed

circuits, assuming a very high ebit fidelity, give values of XEB that are comparable to a perfect quantum computer. To achieve a non-zero XEB, we have seen that we need a fidelity at or above 0.99. Literature has shown that with quantum channel errors of 0.7 and local operation error of 0.1%, this can be achieved through entanglement pumping. This shows that, under certain conditions, distributed entire circuit computation is a viable method of distributed quantum computing. More specifically, we have seen that distributing across more servers introduces more error into the system. It may be difficult to achieve good results with very highly distributed circuits.

We have also seen that the results of our simulations line up with theoretical estimates. Since simulating large distributed circuits is extremely computationally intensive and like infeasible for circuits of more than 40 qubits, this is useful as we can make accurate theoretical predictions.

Future research should focus on creating much more sophisticated error models. We used the depolarising noise model for our ebits but this should be extended with the different types of errors that can happen and made to be more specific to a potential physical manifestation of a distributed quantum computer. Our simulations assumed perfect local operations, including error in our local operations will be necessary for more sophisticated simulations. It will also be important to include the time domain in our errors, including errors such as thermal relaxation error. Creating high-fidelity ebits may be a relatively large part of circuit execution time. If it takes too long, our qubits may simply decohere. Finding the middle ground between decoherence and ebit fidelity will be important.

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